

**Controlling the electrochemical deposition of silver onto gold nanoparticles:
reducing interferences and increasing the sensitivity of magnetoimmuno assays**

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ABSTRACT

An electrocatalytical method induced by gold nanoparticles in order to improve the sensitivity of the magnetoimmunosensing technology is reported. Microparamagnetic beads as primary antibodies immobilisation platforms and gold nanoparticles modified with secondary antibodies as high sensitive electrocatalytical labels are used. A built-in magnet carbon electrode allows the collection / immobilization on its surface of the microparamagnetic beads with the immunological sandwich and gold nanoparticle catalysts attached onto. The developed magnetoimmunosensing technology allows the antigen detection with an enhanced sensitivity due to the catalytic effect of gold nanoparticles on the electroreduction of silver ions. The main parameters that affect the different steps of the developed assay are optimized so as to reach a high sensitive electrochemical detection of the protein. The low levels of gold nanoparticles detected with this method allow the obtaining of a novel immunosensor with low protein detection limits (up to 23 fg / mL), with special interest for further applications in clinical analysis, food quality and safety as well as other industrial applications.

KEYWORDS: Silver electrocatalysis; Gold nanoparticles; Magnetic beads; Electrochemical biosensor; Immunoassay

1. INTRODUCTION

Catalysis is considered as the central field of nanoscience and nanotechnology (Grunes et al., 2003). Interest in catalysis induced by metal nanoparticles (NPs) is increasing dramatically in the last years. The use of NPs in catalysis appeared in the 19th century with photography (use of gold and silver NPs) and the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide (use of PtNPs) (Bradley, 1994). In 1970, Parravano and co-workers (Cha et al., 1970) described the catalytic effect of AuNPs on oxygen-atom transfer between CO and CO₂. Usually, these NP catalysts are prepared from a metal salt, a reducing agent and a stabilizer. Since these first works, NPs have been widely used for their catalytic properties in organic synthesis, for example, in hydrogenation and C-C coupling reactions (Reetz et al., 2004), and the heterogeneous oxidation of CO (Lang et al., 2004) on AuNPs.

On the other hand, immunoassays are currently the predominant analytical technique for the quantitative determination of a broad variety of analytes in clinical, medical, biotechnological, and environmental significance. Recently, the use of metal nanoparticles, mainly gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) as labels for different biorecognition and biosensing processes has received wide attention, due to the unique electronic, optical, and catalytic properties (Wang et al, 2002a; Wang et al., 2003a; Wang et al., 2003c; Liu et al., 2006; Kim et al., 2006; Daniel et al., 2004; Fritzsche et al., 2003; Seydack, 2005). Electrochemical detection is ideally suited for these nanoparticle-based bioassays (Katz et al., 2004; Merkoçi et al., 2005; Merkoçi, 2007) owing to unique advantages related to NPs: rapidity, simplicity, inexpensive instrumentation and field-portability. The use of nanoparticles for multiplex analysis of DNA (Wang et al., 2003b) as well as proteins (Liu et al., 2004) have been also demonstrated showing a great potential of NP applications in DNA and protein studies. A summary of the most

relevant works using AuNPs as label for bioassays along with some relevant results in terms of detection limit (DL) and precision is shown in table 1.

The use of colloidal gold as electrochemical label for voltammetric monitoring of protein interactions was pioneered in 1995 by González-García and Costa-García (González-García et al., 1995), although the first metalloimmunoassay based on a colloidal gold label was not reported until 2000 by Dequaire et al. (Dequaire et al. 2000). Despite the inherent high sensitivity of the stripping metal analysis (Piras et al., 2005) different strategies have been proposed to improve the sensitivity of these metalloimmunoassays. Another protein detection alternative was lastly reported by our group (Ambrosi et al., 2007). This is based on a versatile gold-labeled detection system based on either spectrophotometric or electrochemical method. In our procedure a double codified label (DC-AuNP) based of AuNP conjugated to an HRP-labeled anti-human IgG antibody, and antibodies modified with HRP enzyme is used to detect human IgG as a model protein.

A substantial sensitivity enhancement can be achieved, for example, by using the AuNPs as catalytic labels for further amplification steps. Although an ultrasensitive electrochemical detection immunosensor has been reported recently using the catalytic reduction of p-nitrophenol by AuNP-labels (Das et al., 2006), most common strategy uses the catalytic deposition of gold (Liao et al., 2005) and especially of silver onto AuNPs to improve the sensitivity.

In most cases, the silver enhancement relies on the chemical reduction, mainly using hydroquinone, of silver ions (Karin et al., 2006; Guo et al., 2005; Chu et al., 2005; Chu et al., 2005) to silver metal onto the surface of the AuNPs followed by anodic-stripping electrochemical measurement. However, this procedure is time consuming and its

sensitivity is compromised by nonspecific silver depositions onto the transducing surface.

In 2000, Costa-García and co-workers (Hernández-Santos et al., 2000a,b) reported a novel electrochemical methodology to quantify colloidal gold adsorbed onto a carbon paste electrode based on the electrocatalytic silver deposition. This strategy has been exploited by the same group for a very sensitive immunoassay (De la Escosura-Muñiz et al., 2006) and DNA hybridization detection (De la Escosura-Muñiz et al., 2007) but using a gold (I) complex (aurothiomalate) (De la Escosura-Muñiz et al., 2004) as electroactive label, instead of colloidal gold. Besides the lower time consuming, the silver electrodeposition process shows very interesting advantages over the chemical deposition protocol reported before, since silver only deposits on the AuNPs. This fact results in a high signal-to-background ratio by reducing the nonspecific silver depositions of the chemical procedure.

The electrocatalytic silver deposition on AuNPs has been recently applied in a DNA hybridization assay (Lee et al., 2004; Lee et al., 2005), but till now, to the best of our knowledge, the utilization of this amplification procedure for electrochemical immunoassay detection with AuNP label has not yet been reported.

On the other hand, magnetic particles have been widely used as platforms in biosensing, and the silver chemical deposition approached to improve the sensitivity of the assays (Wang et al., 2001b; Wang et al., 2002b). The magneto based electrochemical biosensors present improved properties in terms of sensitivity and selectivity, due to the preconcentration of the analyte, the separation from the matrix of the sample and the immobilization / collection on the transducer surface, achieved using magnetic fields. However, till now, the utilization of the amplification procedure based on the silver

electrodeposition for the electrochemical detection of AuNPs used as labels in magnetobioassays has not yet been reported.

In this work, an electrocatalytic silver-enhanced metalloimmunoassay using AuNPs as labels and microparamagnetic beads (MB) as platforms for the immunological interaction is developed for model proteins, in order to achieve very low detection limits with interest for further applications in several fields.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1. Apparatus and electrodes

Cyclic voltammetric experiments were performed with an electrochemical analyzer (CH Instrument, USA) connected to a PC. All measurements were carried out at room temperature in a 20 mL cell (protected from light) with a three-electrode configuration. A graphite-epoxy composite electrode with a magnet inside (GECE-M) was used as working electrode. It was prepared as described previously (Cespedes et al., 1993; Santandreu et al., 1997). Briefly, epoxy resin (Epotek H77A, Epoxy Technology, USA) and hardener (Epotek H77B) were mixed manually in the ratio 20:3 (w/w) using a spatula. When the resin and hardener were well-mixed, the graphite powder (particle size 50 μm , BDH, U.K.) was added in the ratio 1:4 (w/w) and mixed for 30 min. The resulting paste was placed into a cylindrical PVC sleeve (6 mm i.d.) incorporating a neodymium magnet (diameter 3 mm, height 1.5 mm, Halde Gac Sdad, Bacelona, Spain, catalog number N35D315) into the body of graphite epoxy composite, 2 mm under the surface of the electrode. Electrical contact was completed using a copper disk connected to a copper wire. The conducting composite was cured at 40 °C for one week. Prior to use, the surface of the electrode was polished with abrasive paper and then with alumina

paper (polishing strips 301044-001, Orion, Spain) and rinsed carefully with bidistilled water. An ultrasonic bath (JP Selecta, Barcelona, Spain) was used to clean the GECE-M surface. A platinum wire as counter electrode and an Ag/AgCl reference electrode were used in the three electrodes configuration. A Metrohm AG Herisau magnetic stirrer was used for the electrochemical pre-treatments, the AuNPs oxidation, the silver electro-deposition and the cleaning step. A Scanning Transmission Microscope (TEM) Jeol JEM-2011 (Jeol Ltd, Tokio, Japan) was used to characterize the magnetic beads after the immunological assay. A Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) Jeol JSM-6300 (Jeol Ltd, Tokio, Japan) coupled to a Energy Dispersive X-Ray (EDX) Spectrophotometer ISIS 200 (Oxford Instruments, Bucks, England) was used to characterize the magnetic beads after the silver electrodeposition.

2.2. Reagents and solutions

Streptavidin-coated Magnetic Beads (M-280) 2.8 μm sized were purchased from Dynal Biotech (Invitrogen, Barcelona, Spain). Biotin conjugate-goat anti-human IgG (Sigma B1140, developed in goat and gamma chain specific), human IgG from serum, goat IgG from serum, anti-human IgG (Sigma A8667, developed in goat is whole molecule), hydrogen tetrachloroaurate(III) trihydrate ($\text{HAuCl}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 99.9%), silver nitrate and trisodium citrate were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. All buffer reagents and other inorganic chemicals were supplied by Sigma, Aldrich or Fluka (Sigma-Aldrich Química, Madrid, Spain), unless otherwise stated. All chemicals were used as received and all aqueous solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water.

The phosphate buffer solution (PBS) consisted of 0.01M phosphate buffered saline, 0.137M NaCl, 0.003M KCl (pH 7.4). Blocking buffer solution consisted of a PBS solution with added 5% (w/v) bovine serum albumin (pH 7.4). The binding and washing (B&W) buffer consisted of a PBS solution with added 0.05% (v/v) Tween 20 (pH 7.4).

The measuring medium for the electrochemical measurements consisted of a 2.0×10^{-4} M silver nitrate solution in 1.0 M NH_3 , prepared in ultra-pure water.

Analytical grade (Merck) NaCl, HCl, H_2SO_4 , NH_3 , KCN and NaOH were used. Their solutions were prepared with ultra-pure water, except for KCN solutions, which were prepared with 0.1 M NaOH.

2.3. Methods

Synthesis of AuNPs and preparation of the conjugated AuNPs/ anti-human IgG

AuNPs were synthesized by reducing tetrachloroauric acid with trisodium citrate, a method pioneered by Turkevich et al. (Turkevich et al., 1951). Briefly, 200 mL of 0.01% HAuCl_4 solution were boiled with vigorous stirring. 5 mL of a 1% trisodium citrate solution were added quickly to the boiling solution. When the solution turned deep red, indicating the formation of AuNPs 15 nm sized, the solution was left stirring and cooling down.

The AuNPs loading with the antibody was performed according to the following procedure: 2 ml of AuNP suspension was mixed with 100 μl of 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ anti-human IgG and incubated at 25 °C for 20 min. After that, a blocking step with 150 μl of 1 mg/ml BSA, incubating at 25 °C for 20 min was performed. Finally, a centrifugation at 14000 rpm for 20 min was carried out, and then the AuNPs/anti-human IgG was reconstituted in H_2O milli-Q.

Previous works in our group (Ambrosi et al., 2007) have recorded transmission electron micrographs (TEM) in order to measure the size, and measured FFT (Fast Fourier Transform) of crystalline planes distances in order to verify the Au metallic structure. The characteristic absorbance peak of gold at 520 nm has been also observed by UV-vis spectrum.

Preparation of the sandwich type immunocomplex

The preparation of the MBs based sandwich type immunocomplex was performed following a method previously optimised in our group, with some improvements. Briefly, 150 μg (15 μL from the stock solution) of MB were transferred into 0.5 mL Eppendorf tube. The MBs were washed twice with 150 μL of B&W buffer. The MBs were then resuspended in 108 μL of B&W buffer and 42 μL (from stock solution 0.36 mg/mL) of biotinylated anti-human IgG were added. The resulting MB and anti-human IgG (goat IgG for the blank assay) solution was incubated for 30 min at temperature 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ with gentle mixing in a TS-100 ThermoShaker. The formed MB/ anti-human IgG were then separated from the incubation solution and washed 3 times with 150 μL of B&W buffer. The preparation process was followed by resuspending the MB/anti-human IgG in 150 μL of blocking buffer (PBS-BSA 5%) to block any remaining active surface of MBs and incubated at 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 60 min. After the washing steps with B&W buffer, the MB/anti-human IgG were incubated at 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 30 min with 150 μL of human IgG antigen at different concentrations, forming by this way the immunocomplex MB/anti-human IgG/Human IgG. Finally, after the washing steps, the MB/anti-human IgG/Human IgG immunocomplex was incubated at 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 30 min with 150 μL of the previously synthesized AuNPs/anti-human-IgG complex. A scheme of this procedure is shown in figure 1.

Electrochemical detection based in the catalytic effect of AuNPs on the silver electro-deposition

The smoothed GECE-M surface was pre-treated before each assay by an electrochemical pre-treatment in 0.1 M HCl. The electrode was immersed in a 0.1 M HCl stirred solution and a potential of +1.25 V was applied for 2 min. After that, the electrode surface was washed with the B&W buffer.

This procedure has been optimized in a previous work for Au(I) complexes (De la Escosura-Muñiz et al., 2004). After the immunoassay protocol was performed, the electrode was immersed in a 0.1 M NaOH solution and held with stirring at +1.25 V for 2 min. Then, the electrode was transferred to a 0.1 M H₂SO₄ solution and held with stirring at +1.20 V for 2 min. After that, the electrode was rinsed with ultra-pure water and introduced in an unstirred 1.0 M NH₃ solution containing silver nitrate at a fixed concentration (2.0×10^{-4} M) and held at a deposition potential of -0.12 V for 60 s. After that, cyclic voltammograms were scanned from deposition potential to +0.30 V at a scan rate of 50 mV s⁻¹. Finally, in order to remove gold from the electrode surface, after each measurement, the GECE-M was immersed in another cell containing a 0.1 M KCN in 0.1 M NaOH (dangerous / hazard solution. This step is made in a fume cupboard) stirred solution for 2 min in open circuit.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Sandwich type immunocomplex

The preparation of the sandwich type immunocomplex was carried out following a previously optimized procedure (Ambrosi et al., 2007), but introducing slight changes in order to minimize the unspecific absorptions that interfere the sensitive electrocatalytic detection. The analytical procedure is described in section *experimental section* and schemed in figure 1.

The use of blocking agents so that any portion of the MB surface which does not contain the primary antibody is "blocked" thereby preventing non-specific binding with the analyte of interest (protein) is crucial. The obtained values of the analytical signals are highly dependent on the blocking quality. Following the previously reported procedure, based on the direct electrochemical detection of AuNP, the blank samples signal (the samples without the antigen or with a non-specific antigen) were very high (data not shown). The resulted unspecific adsorptions could be due to some factors. For a given concentration of the blocking agent the unspecific adsorptions will depend on the time interval used to perform such a step. By increasing the time interval of the blocking step (from 30 to 60 minutes and using PBS-BSA 5% as blocking agent) in the sandwich assay we could ensure a better coverage of the free bounding sites onto the MB surface avoiding by this way the unspecific adsorptions. Another important factor that affects the unspecific adsorptions is the washing step that aims at removing the unbound species avoiding by this way possible signals coming from AuNPs not related to the required antigen. Stirring instead of gentle washing brought significant decrease of unspecific adsorptions too. TEM images of the sandwich assay before and after the mentioned improvement corroborated also in understanding the phenomena related to these non desired adsorptions (see figure S1 in the *supplementary material*).

Clear evidences of the successful immunological reaction in a condition of the absence of unspecific adsorptions are the transmission electron micrographs (TEM) images shown in figure 2. When the assay is carried out in the presence of the non specific antigen (goat IgG - Figure 2A) only MBs are observed with a very low amount of AuNPs non specifically bonded. However, if the assay is performed with the specific antigen (human IgG - Figure 2B), a high quantity of AuNPs is observed around the MBs, which indicates that the immunological reaction has taken place.

3.2. Catalytic effect of AuNPs on the silver electro-deposition

The silver enhancement method, based on the catalytic effect of AuNPs on the chemical reduction of silver ions, has been widely used to improve the detection limits of several metalloimmunoassays. In these assays (Karin et al., 2006; Guo et al., 2005; Chu et al., 2005) the silver ions are chemically reduced onto the electrode surface in the presence of AuNPs connected to the studied bioconjugates, without the possibility to discriminate between AuNP or electrode surface. Furthermore, these methods are time consuming and two different mediums are needed in order to obtain the analytical signal: the silver/chemical reduction medium to ensure the silver deposition and the electrolytic medium necessary to the silver stripping step.

However, in this work, for the first time, the selective electro-catalytic reduction of silver ions on AuNPs is clarified, and the advantages of using MBs as bioreaction platforms combined with the electrocatalytic method are used to design a novel sensing device.

The principle of the electrocatalytic method is resumed in figure 3A. Cyclic voltammograms, obtained by scanning from +0.30 V to -1.20 V in aqueous 1.0 M NH_3 / 2.0×10^{-4} M AgNO_3 , for an electrode without (a) and with (b) AuNPs previously adsorbed during 15 minutes are shown. It can be observed that the half-wave potential of the silver reduction process is lowered when AuNPs are previously deposited on the electrode surface. Under these conditions, there is a difference (ΔE) of 200 mV between the half-wave potential of the silver reduction process on the electrode surface without (a) and with (b) AuNPs are adsorbed on the electrode surface (b). The amount of the catalytic current related to silver reduction increases with the amount of AuNPs adsorbed on the electrode surface (results not shown).

Taking this fundamental behavior into account, a novel analytical procedure for the sensitive detection of AuNPs is designed. It consists in choosing an adequate deposition

potential, i.e. -0.12 V, at which the direct electro-reduction of silver ions, during a determined time, would take place on the AuNPs surface instead of the bare electrode surface. At the beginning of the process, the electrocatalytical reduction of silver ions onto the AuNP surface occurs and once a silver layer is already formed more silver ions are going to be reduced due to a self enhancement deposition. The electrocatalytic process is effective due to the large surface area of AuNPs allowing an easy diffusion and reduction of the silver ions. The proposed mechanism is the following:

In a first step, while applying a potential of -0.12 V during 60 s, the silver from the ammonia complex, are reduced to a metallic silver layer onto the AuNP surface:

In a second step an anodic potential scan is performed (from -0.12 V to +0.30 V) in the same medium, during which the re-oxidation of silver at +0.10 V is recorded:

The amount of silver electrodeposited at the controlled potential (corresponding to deposition onto AuNP surface only) is proportional to the adsorbed AuNPs. Consequently the re-oxidation peak at +0.10 V, produces a current the amount of which is proportional to the AuNP quantity. The obtained re-oxidation peak constitutes thus the analytical signal, used later on for the AuNPs and consequently the protein quantification. The designed AuNP and protein sensing system based on the electrocatalytic reduction of silver presents advantages over the previously reported chemical reduction procedures in terms of higher signal to background ratio and the reduction of the unspecific silver depositions. This behavior is improved by using MBs

as platforms of the bioreactions, since the unspecific AuNPs adsorptions are minimized and at an adequate deposition potential, the silver electrodeposition on the electrode surface is blocked by the MBs.

Thus, following the analytical procedure described in *experimental section* the selective silver deposition onto the AuNPs surface is achieved. The potential and the time of the silver electro-deposition have been previously optimized (see figure S2 in the *supplementary material*). The application of a -0.12 V potential during 60 s resulted the best as a compromise between the higher sensitivity and analysis time.

Typical analytical signals obtained for the sandwich type assay performed with an human IgG concentration of 5.0×10^{-7} $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (a) and for the blank assay performed with the same concentration of goat IgG (b) are shown at figure 3B.

The electrocatalytic deposition of silver ions onto the surface of the magnetic electrode versus the applied potential used for silver deposition is studied also by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Figure 4 shows SEM images of the MB deposited onto the magnetic electrode surface, after performing silver electro-deposition at different deposition potentials (-0.10, -0.12 and -0.20 V) during 1 minute. The upper images of Figure 4 (A,C,E) correspond to the sandwich type assays performed with the non specific antigen (goat IgG - blank assays). The lower part images (B,D,F) correspond to the assays with an specific antigen (human IgG) concentration of $1.0 \cdot 10^{-3}$ $\mu\text{g/mL}$. It can be observed that at a deposition potential of -0.10 V, (A) no silver crystals are formed in the absence of the specific antigen while low amounts of silver crystals (white structures in the B image) are observed with the assay performed with the specific antigen. This means that the silver deposition has scarcely occurred to the AuNPs anchored onto the MB through the immunological reaction. (B). The formation of these silver crystals is much more evident when the same assay (with specific antigen) is performed at

deposition potential of -0.12 V (D) where a bigger amount of MB appear to be covered with silver crystals – the same phenomena not observed for the blank assay (C). The obtained image is clear evidence that the used potential have been adequate for the silver deposition onto the AuNPs attached to the MB through the immunological reaction. The Energy Dispersive X-Ray (EDX) analysis (provided by SEM instrument) is also performed and the results are in agreement with the SEM images. The EDX results confirm the presence of gold and silver only in the assay performed with the specific antigen (see figure S3 in the *supplementary material*). By using more negative deposition potentials (i.e. -0.20 V) the deposition of silver takes place in a high extent also on the electrode surface as it was expected (E). This phenomenon can be appreciated by bigger cluster like white silver crystals that may be associated not only with silver deposited onto the AuNPs but also onto the surface of the magnetic electrode. This potential (-0.20 V) is not adequate to quantify the specific antigen due to false positive results that can be generated. The -0.12 V have been used in our experiments as the optimal deposition potential that can not even discriminate between the assays and the blank but also be able to do protein quantification at a very low detection limit.

Similar silver structures formed onto AuNPs have been earlier after chemical silver (I) reduction for a DNA array-based assay (Park et al., 2002) or an immunoassay (Gupta et al., 2007) but this is the first time that such potential controlled silver deposition induced by the electrocatalytical effect of AuNP are being evidenced. Moreover the relation between the current produced by the oxidation of the selectively deposited silver layer and the quantity of AuNP is demonstrated as see in the following part.

In figure 5A are shown cyclic voltammograms for different concentrations of human IgG following the procedure explained in *experimental section*. Figure 5B represents the corresponding peak heights used as analytical signals,. As observed in this figure a good

linear relationship for the concentrations of human IgG, in the range from 5.0×10^{-8} to 7.5×10^{-7} $\mu\text{g/mL}$, with a correlation coefficient of 0.9969, according to the following equation:

$$ip (\mu\text{A}) = 21.436 [\text{human IgG}] (\mu\text{g/mL}) + 3.750 (n = 3)$$

is obtained.

The limit of detection (calculated as the concentration corresponding to three times the standard deviation of the estimate) of the antigen was 23 fg of human IgG for mL of sample. The reproducibility of the method shows a RSD around 4%, obtained for a series of 3 repetitive immunoreactions for 5.0×10^{-7} μg human IgG / mL.

These results indicate that with the silver enhancement method can be detected 1000 times lower concentrations of antigen than with the direct differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) gold detection (as done by A. Ambrosi et al., 2007]).

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, for the first time, the selective electrocatalytic reduction of silver ions onto the surface of AuNPs is clarified. This catalytic property is combined with the use of microparamagnetic beads as platform for the immobilization of biological molecules, and advantages used to design a novel sensing device. The electrochemical measurement accompanied by scanning electron microscopy images reveal the silver electrocatalysis enhancement by the presence of nanoparticles anchored to the electrode surface through specific antigen-antibody interactions.

In the sensing device, AuNP as label is used to detect human IgG as a model protein and the excess/non-linked reagents of the immunological reactions are separated using a permanent magnet, allowing the electrochemical signal coming from AuNP to be measured, and thus the presence or absence of protein be determined. The magnetic separation step significantly reduces background signal and gives the system distinct advantages for alternative detection modes of antigens. Finally, the sensible electrochemical detection of the AuNPs is achieved, based on their catalytic effect on the electro-reduction of silver ions.

Several problems inherent to the silver electrocatalysis method are resolved by using the magnetic beads as platforms of the bioassays: (i) The selectivity inherent to the use of magnetic beads avoids unspecific adsorptions of AuNPs on the electrode surface, that could give rise to unspecific silver electrodeposition due to the high sensitivity of the amplification method and (ii) In this method, a critical parameter is the silver electrodeposition potential, in order to achieve the silver deposition only on the surface of the AuNPs and not on the electrode surface. In this way, the magnetic beads can block the electrode surface, so the silver electrodeposition on that surface is minimized. The developed electrocatalytic method allows to achieve low levels of AuNPs, so very low protein detection limits, up to 23 fg / mL, are obtained., that are 1000 times lower in comparison to the method based on the direct detection of AuNPs. The novel detection mode allows the obtaining of a novel immunosensor with low protein detection limits, with special interest for further applications in clinical analysis, food quality and safety as well as other industrial applications.

This system establishes a general detection methodology that can be applied to a variety of immunosystems and DNA detection systems, including lab-on-a-chip technology. Currently, this methodology is being applied in our lab for the detection of low concentrations of proteins with clinical interest in real samples.

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FIGURE CAPTIONS

Fig. 1. Schematic (not in scale) of: (A) AuNP conjugation with anti-human IgG; (B) Analytical procedure for the sandwich type assay and the obtaining of the analytical signal based on the catalytic effect of AuNPs on the silver electrodeposition. Procedure detailed in *experimental section*.

Fig. 2. Transmission electron micrographs (TEM) images of the MBs after the sandwich type assay detailed in *experimental section*. Assay carried out with 1.0×10^{-3} $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of the non specific antigen (goat IgG) (blank assay-A-) and assay performed with 1.0×10^{-3} $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of the specific antigen (human IgG) (B).

Fig. 3. (A) Cyclic voltammograms, scanned from +0.30 V to -1.20 V in aqueous 1.0 M NH_3 - 2.0×10^{-4} M AgNO_3 , for an electrode without deposited AuNPs (a-curve) and for an electrode where previously AuNPs have been deposited from the synthesis solution for 15 minutes (b-curve). (B) Cyclic voltammograms recorded in aqueous 1.0 M NH_3 - 2.0×10^{-4} M AgNO_3 , from -0.12 V to +0.30 V for the sandwich type assay described in *experimental section*, with an human IgG concentration of 5.0×10^{-7} $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (b-curve) and with the same concentration of the non specific antigen (goat IgG - blank assay-a-curve). Silver deposition potential: -0.12 V; silver deposition time: 60 seconds; scan rate: 50 mV/s.

Fig. 4. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of the MB deposited on the electrode surface, after the silver electro-deposition in aqueous 1.0 M NH_3 - 2.0×10^{-4} M AgNO_3 , at -0.10 V (A,B,) -0.12 (C,D) and -0.20 V (E,F) during 1 minute, for the sandwich type assay performed as described in *experimental section*, with the non specific antigen (goat IgG -blank assays-A,C,E) and for the specific antigen (human IgG) at concentration of 1.0×10^{-3} $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (B,D,F).

Fig. 5. (A) Cyclic voltammograms recorded in aqueous 1.0 M NH₃-2.0 x 10⁻⁴ M AgNO₃, from -0.12 V to +0.30 V, for the sandwich type assay described in *experimental section* with 1.0 x 10⁻⁶ µg/mL of the non specific antigen (goat IgG -thin line) and for increasing specific antigen (human IgG) concentrations: 5.0 x 10⁻⁸, 1.0 x 10⁻⁷, 5.0 x 10⁻⁷, 7.5 x 10⁻⁷ and 1.0 x 10⁻⁶ µg/mL. Silver electro-deposition potential: -0.12 V; silver deposition time: 60 seconds; scan rate: 50 mV/s. (B) The corresponding relationship between the different concentrations of the human IgG and the obtained peak currents used as analytical signals.

Fig. S1. Transmission electron micrographs (TEM) of the sandwich assay, before (A) and after (B) the improvements in the blocking and cleaning steps. Human IgG concentration: 5.0×10^{-7} $\mu\text{g/ml}$. Rest of experimental conditions as detailed in *experimental section*.

Fig. S2. (A) Relationship between the silver electrodeposition potential and the value of the peak current for a electrodeposition time of 60 seconds. **(B)** Relationship between the silver electrodeposition time and the value of the peak current for a electrodeposition potential of -0.12 V. Grey curves correspond to the blank assay (with the non specific antigen – goat IgG) and black curves correspond to the assay performed with an specific antigen (human IgG). In both cases, the antigen concentration is of $5.0 \times 10^{-7} \mu\text{g/ml}$. Experimental conditions as detailed in *experimental section*.

Fig. S3. Microanalysis data obtained by Energy Dispersive X-Ray Analysis (EDX) coupled to the scanning electron microscope (SEM), of the MBs deposited on the electrode surface, after the silver electro-deposition in aqueous 1.0 M NH_3 - 2.0×10^{-4} M AgNO_3 at -0.12 V for 1 minute, for the sandwich type assay performed with the non specific antigen (goat IgG - blank assay-**A**) and for an specific antigen (human IgG). In both cases the antigen concentration is 1.0×10^{-3} $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (**B**). Silver electro-deposition time: 60 seconds.